

FLOW SWING: A SYSTEM FOR DYNAMIC CONTROL AND EXPLORATION OF NON-ISOCHRONOUS TIMING IN MUSICAL RHYTHMS

George SIOROS¹ and Odysseas KLISSOURAS²

¹University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna (MDW), Vienna, Austria

²aessydo | studio for spatial ideas, Pallini, Greece

ABSTRACT

The representation of timing in commercial digital audio workstations (DAWs) is largely based on isochronous pulses and metrical grids. While some tools support expressive timing adjustments, they typically treat these as deviations from a fixed pulse rather than as fundamental timing structures, limiting their creative and performative scope. Moreover, by enforcing a rigid temporal framework, such systems often marginalize diverse musical traditions and practices.

To address these limitations, we propose an alternative approach built on the existing music-theoretical construct of Non-Isochronous (NI) Grids. NI Grids use a small set of parameters to generate systematic yet expressive rhythmic structures, composed of flexible, non-isochronous reference points. We introduce Flow Swing, a set of Max/MSP patches that implement NI Grids to manipulate the timing of sound samples and control signals. These patches enable precise, real-time time-warping with continuous and dynamic control, allowing for both subtle and extreme transformations, as well as complex alignments across rhythmic streams and polyrhythmic interactions, while integrating seamlessly into the Max/MSP workflow.

By embedding NI Grids into generative and performance-oriented tools, Flow Swing expands the possibilities for rhythmic representation and creative exploration, and pushes against the structural limitations of current music technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

The representation of time in most commercial Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) is fundamentally tied to metrical structures, where musical events are aligned to a hierarchy of isochronous pulses (see [1] for an overview of meter). This framework provides a useful means of organizing rhythm in music traditions that are based on meter, but it fails to accommodate timing practices that do not follow metrical grids. While DAWs offer some flexibility through tools for quantization, these methods primarily model non-isochronous timing as expressive adjustments relative to an

underlying isochronous pulse [1–3], rather than as fundamental rhythmic structures in their own right.

Furthermore, complex rhythmic interactions between voices, such as in polyrhythms and counter-rhythms, are widespread and play an essential role in many popular music styles [4, 5] and traditional music (for examples see [6–8]). However, they are often represented only through their relation to the expected canonical patterns of meter and the different voices are forced into a shared metrical framework. As a result, they are often reduced to a simplistic classification as syncopations, without acknowledging their distinct structural and expressive functions (for definitions of syncopation see [9, 10]).

Despite the diversity of timing practices in music, commercial DAWs lack the tools necessary to represent, manipulate and generate the essential aesthetic features from rhythmic traditions that do not rely on a fixed metrical framework, thereby creating and perpetuating significant biases in music technology [11]. Addressing this challenge requires a shift in approach that moves beyond the static representation of expressing timing as a deviation from isochrony and instead models it as an integral component of rhythm organization.

Several models have been developed to describe non-isochronous timing or micro-timing, focusing on music theoretical concepts [12, 13], cognitive mechanisms [14, 15], and performance analysis [16, 17]. However, most computational models remain based on isochrony, representing timing as metrical templates rather than as independent rhythmic structures (e.g. [18]). An exception is the Non-Isochronous (NI) Grids model [19], which provides a computational framework for generating flexible, non-isochronous reference points from a small set of parameters without imposing a rigid isochronous structure.

In this paper, we implement NI Grids in Max/MSP as an alternative to the metric quantization found in commercial DAWs. We present Flow Swing, a set of two Max/MSP patches for exploring non-isochronous timing in generative and performance contexts. One patch applies time-warping to audio loops, while the other modulates control signals, automation curves and event triggers. By offering alternative ways of representing and manipulating timing, we aim to respond to biases embedded in current music technology and create space for marginalized musical traditions and creative practices.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of existing music technologies and theoretical approaches to the representation and ma-

Copyright: © 2025. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

nipulation of timing in musical rhythm. Section 3 introduces the Flow Swing patches, detailing their design, implementation, and functionality. Section 4 discusses their potential applications in music practice and performance, illustrated through concrete examples. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main contributions of the work.

2. METER AND TIMING

Popular Digital Audio Workstations (DAW) [20, 21] commonly display time either in absolute units (e.g. min::sec) or in relation to a musical meter and time signature. Meter acts as a guide, helping to relate the timing of events to a global tempo and a hierarchy of isochronous pulses of different durations, such as the sixteenth-note pulse or the quarter note pulse. In this hierarchy, the slower pulses are groupings of the faster pulses, e.g. a quarter-note pulse is formed by grouping every fourth sixteenth-note. To move beyond rigid quantitation to metrical subdivisions and allow for more expressive timing, non-isochronous patterns are modeled as deviations from an isochronous pulse. Each metrical position is assigned an "offset" value, so that musical events can be shifted from their on-the-grid positions according to prototypical templates for a particular musical style. Such methods are implemented not only in commercial DAWs, such as the Groove tools in Ableton Live [20] and Reaper [22], but also in non-commercial music systems, e.g. within the Sonic Pi live coding language [18].

These features in music software reflect theoretical models of meter and expressive timing that have been explored in various contexts, from general theoretical frameworks to style specific empirical observations.

Music-theoretical models formalize meter as a hierarchical structure in which rhythmic regularities give rise to isochronous pulses of different periodicities [23]. This hierarchy is manifested in the way that slower pulses coincide with all faster pulses, analogous to the periodic grouping of shorter durations into longer beats. While beats in metrical structures are typically isochronous, non-isochronous beat patterns can be constructed based on the principle of maximal evenness [1, 24, 25]. For example, grouping an isochronous pulse in $3 + 2 + 2$ forms a long-short-short beat structure. Many traditional and popular rhythmic patterns follow this principle [6, 26].

These ideas have been applied to rhythm generation algorithms, allowing rhythmic transformations in symbolic [10, 27, 28] and audio signals [29], and stochastic rhythm generation [30–33]. They have also inspired cognitive models of rhythm perception [1] in which the regularities in rhythm give rise to predictive schemata [9, 34, 35] in the listener's mind. The cognitive analogue of the metrical hierarchy is found in Dynamic Attending Theory [36], where pulses are modeled as oscillations of attentional energy stacked in a hierarchical fashion [37, 38].

While meter maintains a structural isochronicity, the non-isochronous timing of events forms an additional expressive level of organization [2]. This is typically modeled by measuring the inter-onset-intervals (IOI) in repeating rhythmic patterns and deriving statistical properties about the relative duration of beats or their subdivisions within

the duration of the repetition cycle [3]. In [39] for example, the four events of the main repetitive Brazilian Samba pattern were measured in recordings and were found to have systematically different durations. As the four events form the fundamental structural pulse on which the metrical hierarchy is built, it was proposed that the difference in durations of the events directly reflect a difference in durations of the corresponding metrical positions.

The example above is not unique. Non-isochronous metrical subdivisions have been observed and measured in various music practices around the world, from Samba [39–41] and Mali Jembe music [42], to Norwegian Telespringar [43] and Balkan percussion music [44–47]. These measurements capture the subtle and expressive timing variations found in real performances and provide empirical basis for representing timing as it naturally occurs in different musical styles. They are valuable in performance studies as well as in generative tools for music production, e.g. statistical averages of beat durations may be used as templates in a DAW to generate prototypical timing patterns of the respective music styles.

However, while highly descriptive, these models lack predictive power beyond the specific dataset they are based on. They inherently separate structural and expressive components of timing, treating deviations from an isochronous pulse as an additional layer rather than an integral part of the rhythmic framework (see for example the many meters hypothesis in [1, ch. 9]). In this sense, expressive timing is reintroduced post hoc through statistical adjustments rather than been part of a unified model of rhythm. As a result, such models lack the generative rules that could create new rhythmic patterns and make it challenging to extract intuitive musical structures from the data. Furthermore, statistical measurements reduce rhythmic expressivity to a fixed template, overlooking the dynamic timing variations that occur in performance, including rapid fluctuations (for an example of such timing variations see [44]). In commercial DAWs, this is reflected in the static nature of timing adjustments, which remain fixed once applied, rather than allowing real-time manipulation.

2.1 Non-Isochronous Grids

Non-Isochronous Grids (NI) Grids [19] are structures that integrate non-isochronous timing into a systematic framework and establish it as a fundamental organizational principle of rhythm. They are created by morphing between isochronous pulses of different periodicities that are not related through a simple integer ratio, similar to the pulses that make up a polyrhythm. They embed in this way flexible timing directly into the rhythmic organization rather than treating it as an adjustment. A detailed and formal description of NI Grids can be found in [19]. Here, we present those elements that are most relevant to their generative applications.

NI Grids are constructed by shifting the beats of one isochronous pulse, referred to as the Formative pulse, toward the beats of a second isochronous pulse, the Target pulse. This transformation is controlled by a shift parameter S , which determines the degree of displacement for

Figure 1. Formation of an NI Grid through morphing. Adapted from [19]

each beat of the formative pulse. At $S = 0$, the NI Grid coincides with the formative pulse, while at $S = 1$, it is fully aligned with the beats of the target pulse. Intermediate values of S create a gradual morphing effect, producing rhythmic patterns that maintain a structured, non-isochronous distribution of beats (Fig. 1).

A key feature of NI Grids is that they consist of only two distinct time intervals, Short and Long, whose relative number is determined by the relationship between the Formative and Target pulses, and whose relative duration is further shaped by the S parameter. As S goes from 0 to 1, the short intervals become shorter and the long intervals longer. These durations are always distributed as evenly as possible throughout the repetition cycle. However, the maximally even distribution of Short and Long intervals can occur in different rotation variants, each corresponding to a different shift direction of the Formative beats: (1) all beats shifted forward, (2) all shifted backward, or (3) combinations of forward and backward shifts (Fig. 2). The number of possible rotations depends on the relative number of Short and Long beats.

NI Grids are fully defined by four parameters:

1. the number of beats n_F of the Formative pulse within a repetition cycle,
2. the number of beats n_T of the Target pulse,
3. the shift parameter S , and
4. the rotation configuration R of the maximally even Long-Short distribution.

A compact notation for NI Grids is

$$NI(n_F | n_T, S, R)$$

The Formative and Target pulses play distinct roles. The Formative pulse determines the number of beats in the grid, while the combination of Formative and Target pulses determines the number of Long and Short beat durations. For example, an NI Grid $NI(4|5)$ consists of four beats in total—one Long and three Short—whereas $NI(5|4)$ consists of five beats—four Long and one Short.

As a result, the NI Grid is only truly isochronous for $S = 0$, when its beats are aligned with those of the Formative pulse. At the other extreme ($S = 1$), although the beats of the NI Grid are aligned with the beats of the Target pulse, the Long and Short durations have the largest difference. When the Formative pulse has more beats than the Target pulse, the Short interval becomes 0 for $S = 1$, while the Long interval is equal to the beat duration of the

Figure 2. Different alignment configurations between the target and formative pulses result in distinct rotations of the same maximally even Long-Short pattern. In this example, an 8-beat Formative pulse and a 5-beat Target pulse are used. The Formative beats are: (1) all shifted forward, (2) all shifted backward, and (3) shifted to the nearest Target beat.

Target pulse. The resulting grid may appear isochronous, but this is only because the Short intervals are effectively collapsed. When the Formative pulse has fewer beats than the Target pulse, the difference between Long and Short intervals for $S = 1$ is equal to the duration of a Target beat. In this case, the NI Grid can be considered a non-isochronous grouping of the Target pulse, similar to the non-isochronous meters [1] or the Euclidean patterns [6].

NI Grids inherently define non-isochronous timing as part of the rhythmic framework itself. This makes them ideal for generative applications where expressive timing flexibility and systematic structure must coexist. With a dynamic shift parameter S , NI Grids allow real-time modulation of rhythmic patterns and the continuous variation of timing rather than being limited to fixed deviations. Together with the fact that they are defined by a small set of parameters, they can provide a versatile tool for rhythmic generation and performance manipulation. Importantly, beyond their technical applicability, NI Grids have broad musical and cultural relevance, having been successfully applied to non-isochronous timing patterns found in diverse musical traditions, including Brazilian Samba recordings, Balkan music and West African drumming [19, 48, and upcoming publications].

This paper explores their generative potential by implementing NI Grids in two Max/MSP based applications designed for real-time manipulation of sound samples and control signals, described in detail in section 3.

3. FLOW SWING

Flow Swing is a Max/MSP-based tool for flexible timing transformations that is freely accessible on GitHub¹. The main application processes sound samples in real time allowing from subtle timing adjustments that affect the

¹ <https://github.com/sioros/FlowSwing-Max-MSP.git>

Figure 3. The Flow Swing audio wrapper user interface. In the example, the NI Grid is defined by an 8-beat Formative pulse, and a 5-beat Target pulse.

groove or rhythmic "feel" to more drastic time-warping transformations. A sample is segmented automatically or manually and each segment is time-warped and aligned to an NI Grid that can be controlled dynamically and in real time. A second application can process user-defined control signals and events in the same way. Multiple instances of the applications can be used within the Max/MSP environment to create dynamic performances, with intuitive control of the timing and the relations between different rhythmic streams.

The sound sample to be time-warped, whether loaded from disk or recorded in real time, is accessed directly from a Max/MSP buffer. To segment it, warp markers can be inserted manually through the user interface (see Fig. 3, step 1) or automatically through onset detection performed by the Fluid Corpus Manipulation package for Max/MSP [49]. Once a marker has been entered, dragging it to the left or right on the waveform display will stretch/compress the corresponding audio segments to the new durations. The key feature of the application is its ability to "lock" markers to a user-defined NI Grid (Fig. 3, steps 2 & 3). Markers are mapped to the closest formative beat and then aligned to the respective beats of the NI Grid. The timing of the markers and the corresponding time-warping can be further controlled through three parameters in a performance-oriented way:

- *The rotation configuration (R)* (Fig. 3, step 2), which determines how the maximally even pattern of Long and Short beats is rotated. A value of $R = 0$ corresponds to shifting all Formative beats forward to the next Target beat (e.g. Fig. 2, panel 1).
- *The warp strength*, a global parameter in the range $[0., 1.]$ that determines the extent to which each marker is aligned to the NI Grid (Fig. 3, step 3). A value of 0 preserves the user-defined positions, while a value of 1 applies strict alignment with the NI Grid beats.
- *The shift parameter (S)* (Fig. 3, step 4) which modifies the location of the beats of the NI Grid, shifting the positions of the warp markers accordingly.

At the core of the audio warping process is an algorithm implemented in *gen~*, which dynamically and continuously controls playback speed. This enables real-time ad-

Figure 4. The user interface of the control signal Flow Swing patch.

justment of warp markers without interrupting audio playback. Crucially, the algorithm ensures that warped segments remain phase-locked with other sequencers or Flow Swing patches, allowing for seamless integration into complex rhythmic structures.

In addition to the complex time-warping of audio segments, the playback position and overall speed is controlled by a *phase* input that is expected to sweep from 0 to 1 over the duration of the audio buffer. The period of the sweep controls playback speed. When it is set to match the length of the sound sample, the loop retains its original total duration and speed, while individual segments are time-warped according to the positions of the markers. An additional parameter allows a relative offset to be applied to the input *phase*. It can be controlled during performance by pressing and holding down the Hold button which temporarily pauses playback. When released, playback resumes from the position where it was halted, effectively setting a new offset.

Alongside the time-warped audio signal, the application also generates a multichannel trigger signal, with each channel activating at the beginning of a segment. These signals can be used to trigger events, control synthesizers and sequencers, or drive other event-based processes.

The second Flow Swing patch works in a similar way to its audio counterpart, but instead of playing a sound sample, it generates a control signal or automation curve that can be used to modulate parameters in other Max/MSP processes, such as audio synthesizers. The user inserts breakpoints on a 2D plane that can be moved manually or aligned with the beats of an NI Grid to dynamically reshape the timing of the automation. The curve is displayed and edited within a *function* Max/MSP object, connected to a *shape* object to generate a continuous control signal at audio rate.

Similar to the previous audio patch, this second patch also generates a multichannel trigger signal, with each channel activating at a specific breakpoint of the curve.

3.1 Time-warping

Time-warping is implemented using the Max/MSP *groove~* object. However, *groove~* cannot lock its playback position to an input phase because it is limited in the amount of time compression it can apply, and it does not follow the input phase accurately during complex time-warping or real-time adjustment of warp markers. To overcome this limitation, each segment is time-stretched or compressed and played back independently using separate

groove~ objects within the *poly~* system in Max/MSP. The playback speed at each position is continuously calculated in *gen~* and adjusted based on the current input phase and segment endpoint, allowing warp markers to be moved without interrupting playback or affecting synchronization. When the input phase crosses a warp marker, a separate *groove~* object begins playback of the next segment, with a seamless cross-fade between the two.

This method keeps markers coupled to the input phase, even under extreme time compression. In NI Grids where the formative pulse has more beats than the target pulse, and as the shift parameter S approaches 1, multiple formative beats may converge on the same target beat. This causes markers to overlap, collapsing the corresponding segments, which are then skipped during playback.

3.2 Max/MSP integration

The Flow Swing patches are designed to integrate seamlessly within Max/MSP, allowing users to combine them with other Max objects and abstractions. They can be loaded as regular abstractions or within a *bpatcher*, where they can be displayed with either a full interface or a minimal interface that excludes waveform/marker displays and breakpoint functions. All parameters are MIDI-mappable and can be controlled via MIDI CCs or the computer keyboard using Max/MSP's built-in mapping system. Additionally, all parameters are exposed to the *patrr* family of objects, enabling state management and storage of user-inserted warp markers. This also allows patches to communicate via messages, making it possible to link multiple Flow Swing patches together.

To illustrate the integration of Flow Swing patches into a Max/MSP project, we present a simple example demonstrating basic synchronization of complex relationships between rhythmic streams, and event triggering (Fig. 5).

In this example, two sound samples are loaded into *buffer~* objects:

- Flow Swing patches 1 and 2 process the same sample from *buffer~ 1*, but each applies a different set of warp markers and NI Grids, resulting in distinct time-warped outputs.
- Flow Swing patch 3 processes a separate sample from *buffer~ 2*.

A single *phasor~* object controls the overall speed and phase of all three Flow Swing patches, as well as the sequencers. This object generates a periodic ramp that sweeps from 0 to 1, with its period determined by the length of the audio in *buffer~ 1*. This setup ensures that the audio in *buffer~ 2* is automatically stretched or compressed to match the total duration of *buffer~ 1*. In addition, the ramp fed into Flow Swing 2 is modified via *rate~*, which increases its speed, alongside the complex time-warping caused by the marker positions.

The *rate~* multiplier can be set as a fraction, enabling complex alignments and phase drifts in an intuitive way. For instance, using the formative pulse as a reference between two patches, if one Flow Swing patch has 7 beats

Figure 5. A schematic representation of the Max/MSP integration example described in the text. The three Flow Swing patches are shown here with their minimal interface that does not include the waveform display.

and another has 5, setting the first to play at 7/5 the speed of the second ensures that each formative beat has the same duration, while the overall cycle of the first patch is longer.

In addition to audio playback, Flow Swing patches can also be used for event triggering. In this example, the trigger signal from Flow Swing Patch 3 is used to drive a stochastic sequencer that generates events probabilistically, introducing greater rhythmic variation and reducing repetition.

4. DISCUSSION

Defining NI Grids in terms of Formative and Target pulses creates a connection between non-isochronous timing and rhythmic structure, revealing rhythmic relations and interactions that would otherwise be obscured. This enables a richer, more nuanced representation of timing. In this section, we demonstrate how Flow Swing can model complex, yet musically meaningful, relationships within and between rhythmic streams and discuss how timing structures emerge from and relate to the NI Grids configurations.

The dynamic nature of NI Grids allows for the exploration of complex large-scale timing structures and phrasing. For example, an NI Grid can alternate between two different rotation configurations R from one cycle to the next, while keeping other parameters fixed. Fig. 6 shows two states of a Flow Swing device that differ only in the rotation parameter R . Alternating in real time between them results in the temporary "shifting" of the curve points, generating rhythmic variation without altering core NI Grid qualities, such as the durations of the Short and Long beats or the maximally even nature of their distribution. This has conceptual parallels with the phenomenon of syncopation, which can be generated by temporarily displacing events, either by shifting them to weaker metrical positions [10] or by altering the strong-weak accent pattern [33] thereby breaking the expected timing of events without overturning the established meter [9].

While the previous example focused on variations within

Figure 6. Example of a single Flow Swing device that can alternate in real-time between two states with different rotation configurations (top: $R = 0$ and bottom: $R = 2$).

Figure 7. Two NI Grids with Formative pulses (F) forming an 8|6 polyrhythm (equivalent to 4|3), and Target pulses (T) consisting of 5 beats each. When both NI Grids share the same S value, the beats marked with (*) remain aligned, regardless of the value of S , while the remaining beats form more complex timing relationships. In this example, $S = 0.5$.

a single rhythmic stream, NI Grids can also be used to model relationships between multiple streams. Consider the example in Fig. 7. Intermediate S values establish particular relations between the beats of the two NI Grids, with some beats aligned and some not. The combination of their Formative pulses creates an identifiable 8|6 polyrhythm, which is most clearly heard when $S = 0$. As S increases, this polyrhythmic character persists, even though the actual beat positions no longer align with the 8- or 6-beat pulse. However, as S approaches 1, both NI Grids converge towards a 5-beat cycle defined by their Target pulses and the polyrhythmic relationship between the two streams fades.

A more complex example is shown in Fig. 8. As in the previous example, the two Formative pulses form a common polyrhythm, 4|6 or 2|3. This time, however, the combination of the Target pulses also creates a polyrhythm: specifically 5|4. At the two extremes, $S = 0$ and $S = 1$, the two polyrhythms are clearly identifiable. The beats of the two NI Grids are consistently interleaved in both the 4|6 and 5|4 polyrhythms, although the precise timing differs between them. While this interleaving is structurally maintained across all S values, changes in S alter the placement of individual beats. For intermediate values of S , the timing no longer corresponds exactly to either polyrhythm, and the resulting patterns can be understood as blending features of both structures.

Figure 8. Two NI Grids with formative pulses (F) forming an 8|6 polyrhythm, and target pulses (G) forming a 5|4 polyrhythm. As the value of S increases, one polyrhythm morphs gradually into the other.

Consider, for example, the third beat of $NI(4|5)$ and the third and fourth beats of $NI(6|4)$. As the third beat of $NI(4|5)$ shifts out of alignment with the fourth beat of $NI(6|4)$, the 5|4 polyrhythm becomes more pronounced, and an interplay emerges between a five-beat (quinary) structure and a binary subdivision. At the same time, the third and fourth beats of $NI(6|4)$ suggest a ternary subdivision, characteristic of the 4|6 polyrhythm. As the interval between them decreases, this ternary character gradually fades. Taken together, intermediate values of S produce a flexible temporal pattern in which the interleaved structure continues to suggest elements of both polyrhythms, resulting in a rich, and musically coherent rhythmic texture.

Polyrhythms may be understood as the interaction of two or more pulses with different tempos. This perspective does not fully apply to NI Grids. When S is close to 0 or 1, an NI Grid conveys a sense of an isochronous pulse, as its beats closely align with either the Formative or the Target pulse. Since these two pulses have different tempos, the NI Grid inherits a distinct tempo at each extreme. However, for intermediate values of S , this clear sense of tempo becomes blurred. The perceived tempo of the NI Grid does not vary linearly with S ; for instance, at $S = 0.5$, its tempo is not simply the average of the two. In fact, the concept of tempo may not be meaningfully applicable to NI Grids at intermediate S values. Polyrhythmic structures that arise from the interaction of multiple NI Grids may also be difficult to interpret as the interplay of distinct isochronous pulses. Nevertheless, the way their beats interweave can still evoke the sensation of a complex polyrhythm.

5. CONCLUSION

As a first step in addressing biases in commercial music production tools, we propose a novel performance and production paradigm that abandons the fixed reference points commonly based on meter in favor of the dynamic Non-Isochronous Grids framework. To this end we developed Flow Swing: two max/MSP patches that implement NI Grids to time-warp sound samples and automation curves.

A key advantage of Flow Swing is their dynamic adaptability, allowing for continuous variation in timing rather than fixed deviations. This makes them well-suited for capturing both subtle and pronounced timing shifts within a performance. Unlike statistical models that impose deviations onto an isochronous reference, NI-grids inherently

shape the rhythmic structure itself.

The structures generated by NI Grids have been shown to closely replicate the timing patterns found in various musical traditions from around the world, including those under-represented in commonly adopted music software systems (see section 2.1). Flow Swing opens up new possibilities for integrating non-isochronous timing into diverse musical practices. By providing a flexible and adaptive rhythmic framework, it has the potential to support musicians and producers, bridging the gap between current music technology and the rhythmic complexity present in their music.

Section 4 presented three examples in which Flow Swing enables the exploration of intricate timing patterns and interactions, both within and between rhythmic streams. In these examples, the ways in which the beats of the NI Grids interweave are difficult to conceptualize through timing patterns alone or by treating their timing as mere deviations from an isochronous pulse. As not all beats are necessarily articulated, and because the S parameter can vary independently across grids, these interactions can be even more complex and dynamic. Crucially, Flow Swing provides a performative and interactive context in which such relationships can be discovered and explored, transforming them from abstract theoretical constructs into tangible creative tools. The NI Grid framework enables complex rhythmic relationships to be effectively encoded with a limited set of parameters and creatively explored through the Flow Swing patches.

In addition, Flow Swing can serve as a valuable tool in laboratory experiments, facilitating the study of rhythmic perception and performance by generating controlled variations of timing patterns and musical examples. In the future, the continued development of Flow Swing, both as a creative tool and as a research instrument, can contribute to a more inclusive, flexible and nuanced approach to rhythmic representation in both artistic and scientific domains.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] J. London, *Hearing in time: Psychological Aspects of Musical Meter*. Oxford University Press Inc., 2004.
- [2] E. F. Clarke, “Levels of structure in the organization of musical time,” *Contemporary Music Review*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 211–238, Jan. 1987.
- [3] K. Hellmer and G. Madison, “Quantifying Microtiming Patterning and Variability in Drum Kit Recordings: A Method and Some Data,” *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 147–162, Dec. 2015.
- [4] G. Sioros, G. Madison, D. Cocharro, A. Danielsen, and F. Gouyon, “Syncopation and Groove in Polyphonic Music: Patterns Matter,” *Music Perception*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 503–531, Jun. 2022.
- [5] A. Danielsen, *Presence and Pleasure: The Funk Grooves of James Brown and Parliament*. Middletown, CT: Wesleyan University Press, 2006.
- [6] G. T. Toussaint, “The Euclidean algorithm generates traditional musical rhythms,” in *Proceedings of BRIDGES: Mathematical Connections in Art, Music and Science*, Banff, Alberta., Canada, 2005, pp. 47–56.
- [7] S. Arom, *African polyphony and polyrhythm*. Cambridge University Press, 1991.
- [8] M. Yeston, *The Stratification of Musical Rhythm*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, Feb. 1976.
- [9] D. Huron, *Sweet anticipation: music and the psychology of expectation*. Cambridge, Massachusetts / London, England: The MIT Press, 2006.
- [10] G. Sioros, M. E. P. Davies, and C. Guedes, “A generative model for the characterization of musical rhythms,” *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 114–128, Mar. 2018.
- [11] G. Born, “Diversifying MIR: Knowledge and Real-World Challenges, and New Interdisciplinary Futures,” *Transactions of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 193–204, 2020.
- [12] C. D. Stover, “A theory of flexible rhythmic spaces for diasporic African music,” PhD, University of Washington, 2009.
- [13] A. Danielsen, M. Johansson, and C. Stover, “Bins, Spans, and Tolerance: Three Theories of Microtiming Behavior,” *Music Theory Spectrum*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 181–198, Sep. 2023.
- [14] T. Kaplan, L. Jamone, and M. Pearce, “Probabilistic modelling of microtiming perception,” *Cognition*, vol. 239, p. 105532, Oct. 2023.
- [15] A. McGuinness, “Modelling Microtiming Beat Variations with Pulse-Coupled Oscillators,” *Timing & Time Perception*, vol. 3, no. 1-2, pp. 155–171, May 2015.
- [16] G. S. Câmara, G. Sioros, and A. Danielsen, “Mapping timing and intensity strategies in drum-kit performance of a simple back-beat pattern,” *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 3–26, Jan. 2022.
- [17] G. Sioros, G. S. Câmara, and A. Danielsen, “Mapping Timing Strategies in Drum Performance,” in *20th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR)*, Delft, The Netherlands, 2019, pp. 776–783.
- [18] M. Johnson and M. Gotham, “Musical micro-timing for live coding,” in *Proc. of the 24th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf.*, Milan, Italy, 2023.
- [19] G. Sioros, “Polyrhythmic modelling of non-isochronous and microtiming patterns,” in *Proceedings of the 24th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, Milan, Italy, 2023.
- [20] “Live,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ableton.com/>

- [21] “REAPER,” Feb. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.reaper.fm/>
- [22] “Fingers Groove Tool,” 2010. [Online]. Available: https://wiki.cockos.com/wiki/index.php/Fingers_Groove_Tool
- [23] F. Lerdahl and R. Jackendoff, *A Generative Theory of Tonal Music*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 1983.
- [24] J. Clough and J. Douthett, “Maximally Even Sets,” *Journal of Music Theory*, vol. 35, no. 1/2, pp. 93–173, 1991.
- [25] R. Cohn, “A Platonic Model of Funky Rhythms,” *Journal of the Society for Music Theory*, vol. 22, no. 2, 2016.
- [26] G. T. Toussaint, *The Geometry of Musical Rhythm: What Makes a “Good” Rhythm Good?* Chapman and Hall/CRC, Jan. 2013.
- [27] G. Sioros and C. Guedes, “Syncopation as Transformation,” in *Sound, Music and Motion*. Springer International Publishing, 2014, vol. 8905, pp. 635–658.
- [28] G. Sioros, M. Miron, D. Cocharro, C. Guedes, and F. Gouyon, “Syncopalooza : Manipulating the Syncopation in Rhythmic Performances,” in *10th International Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 10. Marseille, France: Laboratoire de Mécanique et d’Acoustique, 2013, pp. 454–469.
- [29] D. Cocharro, G. Sioros, M. Caetano, and M. E. Davies, “Real-time Manipulation of Syncopation in Audio Loops,” in *Joint ICMC 2014 / SMC 2014*, 2014.
- [30] C. Barlow and H. Lohner, “Two essays on theory,” *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 44–60, 1987.
- [31] C. Barlow, “Corrections for Clarence Barlow’s Article: Two Essays on Theory,” *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. 10, 1987.
- [32] G. Sioros and C. Guedes, “A formal approach for high-level automatic rhythm generation,” in *Proceedings of Bridges 2011: Mathematics, Music, Art, Architecture, Culture*. Coimbra, Portugal: Tessellations Publishing, 2011, pp. 233–240.
- [33] —, “Automatic rhythmic performance in Max/MSP: the kin. rhythmicator,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME)*, Oslo, Norway, 2011, pp. 88–91.
- [34] S. Koelsch, P. Vuust, and K. Friston, “Predictive Processes and the Peculiar Case of Music,” *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 63–77, 2019.
- [35] R. Parncutt, “A perceptual model of pulse salience and metrical accent in musical rhythms,” *Music Perception*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 409–464, 1994.
- [36] M. R. Jones, “Musical time,” in *The oxford handbook of music psychology*. New York: Oxford University Press, Dec. 2008, pp. 81–92.
- [37] E. W. Large and M. R. Jones, “The dynamics of attending: How people track time-varying events.” *Psychological Review*, vol. 106, no. 1, pp. 119–159, 1999.
- [38] E. W. Large, “Neurodynamics of Music,” in *Music Perception*, 2010, vol. 36, pp. 201–231.
- [39] M. R. Haugen and A. Danielsen, “Effect of tempo on relative note durations in a performed samba groove,” *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 349–361, Aug. 2020.
- [40] L. Naveda, F. Gouyon, C. Guedes, and M. Leman, “Microtiming Patterns and Interactions with Musical Properties in Samba Music,” *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 225–238, Sep. 2011.
- [41] G. Guillot, “Multi-level Anisochrony in Afro-Brazilian music,” *GMTH Proceedings*, pp. 406–421, 2022.
- [42] R. Polak, “Rhythmic Feel as Meter. Musical Examples,” *Music Theory Online*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 1–34, 2010.
- [43] M. R. Haugen, “Investigating Musical Meter as Shape: Two Case Studies of Brazilian Samba and Norwegian Telespringar,” in *Proceedings of the 25th Anniversary Conference of the European Society for the Cognitive Sciences of Music*, Ghent, Belgium, 2017, pp. 67–74.
- [44] N. Bernackı, “Microtiming Analysis of Two Dance-Songs from the Pirin-Macedonia Region of Bulgaria,” *Conservatorium / Konservatorium Special Issue*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 76–86, Nov. 2023.
- [45] D. Goldberg, “Timing Variations in Two Balkan Percussion Performances,” *Empirical Musicology Review*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 305–328, Jan. 2016.
- [46] —, “Timing of Unequal Beats in Bulgarian Drumming,” *GMTH Proceedings*, pp. 380–392, 2022.
- [47] R. Polak, “Pattern and Variation in the Timing of Aksak Meter: Commentary on Goldberg,” *Empirical Musicology Review*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 329–340, Jan. 2016.
- [48] G. Sioros, “Non-isochronous grids: Connecting microtiming, maximal evenness and polyrhythms,” in *Rhythm under the Microscope: An Interdisciplinary Conference on Microrhythm and Groove in Popular Music*, Vienna, Austria, 2024.
- [49] P. A. Tremblay, O. Green, G. Roma, J. Bradbury, T. Moore, J. Hart, and A. Harker, “The Fluid Corpus Manipulation Toolbox,” Jul. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6834643>